

Organic Derivatives of Boron. Part III. Trimethylene and Propylene Glycol Derivatives

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Several alkyltrimethylene and alkyl propylene borates have been prepared. The lower members have been found to show a low stability to heat, whereas the higher members are quite stable. Di-trimethylene trimethylene di(borate) and di-propylene propylene di(borate) have also been synthesised.

Mixed cyclic orthoborates were for the first time prepared by Thomas¹ from ethylene glycol or catechol and boron trioxide. Recently, alkylethylene borates have been prepared by the action of alcohols on ethylene chloroboronate² and alkyl *o*-phenylene borates have been prepared either by the reaction of alcohols on *o*-phenylene chloroboronate³ or from ethyl *o*-phenylene borate by alcohol interchange⁴. In this communication, attempts have been made to prepare cyclic orthoborate derivatives from trimethylene glycol and propylene glycol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Analytical procedures have been described before⁵. Glycols were distilled before use. Ethyl borate was prepared from boron trichloride and ethanol. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in a semi-micro ebulliometer (Gallenkamp) in benzene.

Reactions between Ethyl Borate and Trimethylene Glycol

(i). Trimethylene glycol (9.09 g., 1 *M*) was added to ethyl borate (17.5 g., 1 *M*) in benzene (50 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours and then slowly fractionated, furnishing 9.95 g. of ethanol (2 moles require 11.02 g.) in the azeotrope. Excess of benzene was distilled and the remaining liquid was kept at 28°/1 mm for 2 hrs., when 14 g. of a colorless liquid (Found: B, 8.0%) was obtained. On its distillation, two fractions were obtained. At first, *ethyl trimethylene borate*, a colorless liquid (7 g.), was obtained at 50-75°/2 mm. (Found: B, 8.10; C₂H₅O*, 31.2. C₅H₁₁BO₃ requires B, 8.32; C₂H₅O, 34.6%) and then *di-trimethylene trimethylene di(borate)*, a colorless heavy liquid (3.7 g.), was obtained at 142°/0.2 mm. (Found: B, 8.62. C₅H₁₀B₂O₆ requires B, 8.86%).

(ii). Trimethylene glycol (3.90 g., 3 *M*) was added to ethyl borate (5.0 g., 2 *M*) in benzene (40 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs. and then slowly fractionated, afford-

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 820, 833.
2. Blau *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1957, 4116.
3. Gerrard *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, 1529.
4. Mehrotra and Srivastava, *ibid.*, 1961, 4045.
5. Mehrotra and Srivastava, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 1.

ing 4.51 g. ethanol (6 moles require 4.72 g.) in the azeotrope at 68°. After removing excess of benzene, the compound was kept at 30°/1 mm for 2 hrs., when a colorless heavy liquid (4.4 g., found: B, 8.4%) was obtained. On its distillation, di-trimethylene trimethylene di(borate) was obtained at 150°/0.6 mm. (Found: B, 8.75; M.W., 240. $C_6H_{12}B_2O_6$ requires B, 8.86%; M.W., 244).

(iii). Trimethylene glycol (4.9 g., 2 *M*) was added to ethyl borate (4.7 g., 1 *M*) in benzene (40 g.) and the mixture after being refluxed for 2 hrs. was fractionated. The azeotrope coming at 68° yielded 4.3 g. ethanol (3 moles require 4.44 g.). After removing excess of benzene, the compound was dried at 35°/0.5 mm for 2 hrs., when 3-hydroxypropyltrimethylene borate, a colorless heavy liquid, was obtained (5.02 g., 97%). (Found: C, 44.0; H, 7.9; B, 6.9. $C_6H_{13}BO_4$ requires C, 45.0; H, 8.1; B, 6.76%). This compound (3.4 g.) yielded *sn* distillation a colorless liquid (0.6 g.) at 90-100°/1.5 mm. (Found: B, 1.2%) and di-trimethylene trimethylene di(borate) (2.2 g.) at 150°/0.6 mm (Found: B, 8.71 %).

Alkyl Trimethylene Borates

Propylⁱ Trimethylene Borate.—A mixture of boric acid (7.40 g., 1 *M*), trimethylene glycol (8.85 g., 1 *M*), and isopropanol (50 g.) was refluxed for 2 hrs. and then slowly fractionated. After taking out water-isopropanol azeotrope, excess of isopropanol was rapidly distilled and finally the remaining liquid was distilled at a reduced pressure when two fractions were obtained: (i) *Propylⁱ trimethylene borate* (2.8 g.) at 50-70°/1.5 mm (Found: B, 7.48; C_3H_7O , 38.5%. $C_6H_{13}BO_3$ requires B, 7.51; C_3H_7O , 40.9%); (ii) the second fraction (4.4 g.) at 156°/0.8 mm. (Found: B, 8.66%).

Propylⁿ Trimethylene Borate.—A mixture of boric acid (5.0 g., 1 *M*), trimethylene glycol (6.17 g., 1 *M*), and *n*-propanol (40 g.) on being refluxed and distilled as in the above experiment yielded *propylⁿ trimethylene borate* (6 g.) at 50-80°/1 mm. (Found: B, 7.35; M.W., 147. $C_6H_{13}BO_3$ requires B, 7.51%; M.W., 144) and di-trimethylene trimethylene di(borate) (1.3 g.) at 160°/0.9 mm (Found: B, 8.68%).

Butyl esters (*n*- and *sec.*) were prepared in the same way as the propyl (*n*- and *iso*) derivatives and were distilled without decomposition. For preparing higher esters, an equimolar mixture of the glycol, boric acid, and alcohol was refluxed in benzene and after distilling water-benzene azeotrope and excess of benzene, the compound was distilled at a reduced pressure. The essential details are recorded in Table I.

Butylⁿ trimethylene borate was also prepared by refluxing a mixture of butylⁿ borate (6.24 g., 1 *M*) and trimethylene glycol (2.06 g., 1 *M*) and distilling *n*-butanol (3.8 g.) at 115-18° and finally the borate (4.0 g., 93%) at 75-80°/0.6 mm. (Found: B, 6.71; M.W., 145. $C_7H_{15}BO_3$ requires B, 6.84%; M.W., 158).

Amyl^{sec} trimethylene borate was prepared by alcohol interchange between ethyl trimethyleneborate (3.1 g.) and amyl^{sec} alcohol (2.2 g.). The mixture in benzene (40 g.)

*Ethoxy (and isopropoxy) estimations have been carried out by estimating the ethanol (or isopropanol) oxidimetrically after being fractionated azeotropically with benzene when the compound is refluxed with water or a higher alcohol. As could be expected, there is a loss of some ethanol (or isopropanol) under the conditions and hence the experimental results for these are slightly lower (6-10%) than the theoretical values.

was refluxed for an hour and then slowly fractionated yielding 0.9 g. ethanol (83%) in the azeotrope. After removing excess of benzene, the remaining liquid was distilled when amyl^{sec} trimethylene borate (3.2 g.) was obtained at 54°/0.1 mm. (Found: B, 6.15; M.W., 175. $C_8H_{17}BO_3$ requires, B, 6.28%; M.W., 172).

TABLE I

Alkyl trimethylene borates.

Ester.	B.P.	% Yield (distillate).	% Boron.		Mol. wt.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
$C_4H_9^p$	73-75°/0.5mm	88	6.70	6.84	160	158
$C_4H_9^{sec}$	50-70°/0.9	80	6.88	6.84	161	158
$C_3H_{11}^n$	78-86°/1.0	91	6.16	6.28	170	172
2-Octyl	97-105°/1.0	95	4.99	5.05	220	214
Cyclohexyl	87-91°/0.8	93	5.87	5.88	189	184
C_6H_5	99-102°/0.3	87	5.90	6.07	180	178
$C_6H_5CH_2$	109-20°/0.4	80	5.57	5.63	191	192
$C_6H_5CH_2CH_2$	113-17°/0.2	90	5.28	5.25	210	206

Reactions between Ethyl Borate and Propylene Glycol

(i). Propylene glycol (4.95 g., 1M) was added to ethyl borate (9.52 g., 1M) in benzene (40 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs. and then slowly fractionated, yielding 5.72 g. ethanol (2 moles require 5.99 g.) in the azeotrope. After distilling the excess of benzene, the compound was distilled at a reduced pressure when two fractions were obtained. First fraction, *ethyl propylene borate* (4.1 g.) distilled at 36-39°/2 mm. (Found: B, 8.41; C_2H_5O , 32.0. $C_5H_{11}BO_3$ requires B, 8.32; C_2H_5O , 34.6%). The second fraction, *dipropylene propylene di(borate)* (1.3 g.) was obtained at 115-17°/0.5 mm. (Found: B, 8.90. $C_5H_{12}B_2O_6$ requires B, 8.86%).

(ii). Propylene glycol (4.42 g., 3M) was added to ethyl borate (5.66 g., 2M) in benzene (40 g.). The mixture after being refluxed for 2 hrs. was fractionated; 5.01 g. ethanol (6 moles require 5.35 g.) was obtained in the azeotrope. After removing excess of benzene, the compound was distilled when dipropylene propylene di(borate), a colorless heavy liquid (4.0 g., 84%), was obtained at 115°/0.4 mm. (Found: B, 8.9; M.W., 241. $C_5H_{12}B_2O_6$ requires B, 8.86%; M.W., 244).

Alkyl Propylene Borates

Isopropyl Propylene Borate.—A mixture of propylene glycol (5.1 g., 1M), boric acid (4.16 g., 1M), and isopropanol (35 g.) was refluxed for 2 hrs. and then slowly fractionated. After distilling the water—*isopropanol* azeotrope and excess of isopropanol, the remaining liquid, on distillation under reduced pressure, afforded *isopropyl Propylene borate* (4.5 g.) at 50-70°/5 mm. (Found: B, 7.60; C_3H_7O , 38.2. $C_6H_{13}BO_3$ requires B, 7.51; C_3H_7O , 40.9%) and dipropylene propylene di(borate) (3.4 g.) at 130°/3 mm (Found: B, 8.90%).

Propyl Propylene Borate.—A mixture of propylene glycol (5.51 g., 1M), boric acid (4.5 g., 1M), and *n*-propanol (30 g.), on being refluxed and distilled as in the above experiment, yielded *propyl propylene borate* (7.3 g.) at 47-50°/1 mm. (Found:

B, 7.61; M.W., 146. $C_6H_{13}BO_3$ requires B, 7.51%; M.W., 144) and dipropylene propylene di(borate) (0.5 g.) at 120°/0.8 mm. (Found: B, 8.92%).

Butyl esters (*n*- and *sec*.) were prepared in the same way, whereas for the preparation of higher esters, an equimolar mixture of the glycol, boric acid, and alcohol in benzene was refluxed; water—benzene azeotrope and excess of benzene were distilled and finally the compound was distilled under reduced pressure. The essential details are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Alkyl propylene borates.

Ester.	B.P.	Yield. (distillate)	% Boron.		Mol. wt.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
$C_4H_9^a$	58-60°/1.0 mm	90	6.88	6.84	161	158
$C_4H_9^{sec}$	65-68°/3.0	85	6.91	6.84	156	158
$C_3H_7^a$	67-71°/0.4	94	6.28	6.28	174	172
2-Octyl	88-94°/0.8	97	5.98	5.95	218	214
Cyclohexyl	81-82°/0.7	93	5.90	5.88	182	184
C_6H_5	99-100°/0.3	80	6.01	6.07	190	178
$C_6H_5CH_2$	100-112°/0.4	87	5.70	5.63	195	192
$C_6H_5CH_2CH_2$	116-22°/0.5	91	5.30	5.25	203	206

Butyl^a propylene borate was also prepared from butyl^a borate. A mixture of butyl^a borate (8.36 g., 1M) and propylene glycol (2.8 g., 1M) was refluxed for 2 hours; *n*-butanol produced (5 g.) was distilled slowly and finally butyl^a propylene borate was distilled at 41-47°/0.3 mm; yield 4.6 g. (80%). (Found: B, 6.85; M.W., 150. $C_7H_{13}BO_3$ requires B, 6.84%; M.W., 158).

Amyl^{sec} propylene borate was prepared by alcoholic interchange between ethyl propylene borate (1.65 g.) and *amyl^{sec} alcohol* (1.3 g.). The mixture in benzene (30 g.) was refluxed for 2 hrs. and then slowly fractionated, affording 0.49 g. ethanol (1 mole requires 0.57 g.) in the azeotrope. Distillation of the remaining liquid yielded the borate (1.5 g.) at 45-47°/0.1 mm. (Found: B, 6.16; M.W., 170. $C_8H_{17}BO_3$ requires B, 6.28%; M.W., 172).

DISCUSSION

Refluxing of an equimolar mixture of ethyl borate and trimethylene glycol in benzene medium, removal of ethanol produced azeotropically, and subsequent distillation of the product gave ethyl trimethylene borate and di-trimethylene trimethylene di(borate). The reaction in 2:3 molar ratio yielded di-trimethylene trimethylene di(borate) quantitatively (I), whereas 3-hydroxypropyl trimethylene borate was formed by the reaction in molar ratio of 1:2 (II) which, when heated, decomposed to afford the diborate.

Alkyl trimethylene borates may be conveniently prepared by refluxing an equimolar mixture of the glycol, boric acid, and alcohol and distilling the water formed during the reaction azeotropically either with excess of alcohol itself [in case of lower alcohols, e.g., propanols (*n*- and *iso*) and butanols (*n* and *sec.*)] or with benzene (III). Butylⁿ trimethylene borate is obtained also by the reaction between butylⁿ borate and the glycol in equimolar ratio (IV). Reactions similar to above have been found with propylene glycol (V).

Lower members of the alkyl trimethylene borate as well as the alkyl propylene borate series [e.g., ethyl and propyl (*n* and *iso*)] derivatives have low stability to heat and decompose during distillation to furnish the diborate. Higher members and the diborates are sufficiently stable. All the compounds are colorless, monomeric liquids which hydrolyse readily and completely on exposure.

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